

Research Article

Importance of chemical laboratories in public schools authorized by higher education institutions: A case study of school students and teachers

Azra Soomro^{1*}, Faiza Hisbani¹, Imtiaz Ali Mallah², Quratulain Abro¹, Lutif Rehman², Paras Rani Mahar²

¹Mehran University of Engineering & Technology Jamshoro Sindh, Pakistan

²University of Sindh Jamshoro Sindh, Pakistan

***Corresponding author:**

azrasoomro@hotmail.com

Accepted: 01 June, 2020; Online: 10 June, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3887362>

Abstract: This paper presents that chemistry has been identified to be one of the major foundations for the transformation of our national economy, and hence must be accorded adequate attention. In this study, an attempt was made in ascertaining the remote causes for the poor performances reported in recent times in chemistry at the secondary level of education in schools. In this regard the data were collected by comparing two schools, Model school Hyderabad (Elsa Kazi Campus) and Mehran public secondary School Jamshoro from students and chemistry teachers, variables were investigated and the findings showed that the laboratories facilities including equipment and chemicals are not proper. The descriptive method was used which includes Quantitative approach and observation technique. And these all contribute greatly from the response of students and teachers in science subject chemistry in particular. The laboratory experiences have been maintained to promote central science education goals including the enhancement of students understanding of concepts in science (Chemistry) and its applications; scientific practical skills and problem solving abilities; scientific habits of mind, understanding of how science and scientists work, interest and motivation. It is necessary to implement the best planning for the chemistry learning and improve the students learning capabilities.

Keywords: Higher education institutions, quantitative approach, chemical laboratories

1. Introduction

Science education is the field concerned with sharing science content and process with individuals not traditionally considered part of the scientific community [1]. The learners may be children, college students, or adults within the general public; the field of science education includes work in science content, science process (the scientific method). Chemistry is the study

of chemicals and the elements and their effects and attributes. Students in chemistry learn the periodic table. The branch of science education says that "chemistry must be taught in a relevant context in order to promote full understanding of current sustainability issues. As this source states chemistry is a very important subject in school as it teaches students to understand issues in the world. As children are interested by the world around them chemistry teachers can attract interest in turn educating the students further. The subject of chemistry is a very practical based subject meaning most of class time is spent working or completing experiments. It is also believed that laboratory teaching and experiments that are being conducted there help encourage deep understanding in children [1-3]. It is also found that school science lab equipment and supplies make teaching and learning easy both for the teachers, as well as for the students. (Report: Jan 12, 2015): Laboratory work is considered essential in promoting students' learning of science and of scientific inquiry. What the students perceive as important to learn from a regular laboratory exercise is probably affected by the teacher's objectives. We study the extent to which one teacher's objectives are fulfilled during lab work, and how teacher–student and student–student interactions contribute to developing learning experiences from the laboratory exercise. Especially teacher–student interactions during lab work seemed to influence what students perceived as important to learn [4]. In the laboratory exercise in this case, the teacher helped the students to observe and to use their observations in their explanations. The lab work included learning experiences other than those addressed by the teacher, and the teacher's intentions were partially fulfilled. Not only what the teacher says, but also how the teacher acts is important to help students understand what to learn from a laboratory exercise [5]. Teaching is the process of attending to people's needs, experiences and feelings, and making specific interventions to help them learn particular things. Interventions commonly take the form of questioning, listening, giving information, explaining some phenomenon, demonstrating a skill or process, testing understanding and capacity, and facilitating learning activities (such as note taking, discussion, assignment writing, simulations and practice). Science education is the field of science that is concerned with sharing of science content, some social science, and the process of teaching science pedagogy in order to provide expectations for the development of understanding part of the scientific community [6]. Teaching and learning of natural sciences is very important field. Chemistry laboratory work is considered essential in promoting students' learning of science and of scientific inquiry. What the students perceive as important to learn

from a regular laboratory exercise is probably affected by teachers' objectives [7]. We study the extent to which one teacher's objectives are fulfilled during lab work, and how teacher-student and student-student interactions contribute to developing learning experiences from the laboratory exercise. Especially teacher-student interactions during lab work seemed to influence what students perceived as important to learn [8]. In the laboratory exercise in this case, the teacher helped the students to observe and to use their observations in their explanations [9]. The lab work included learning experiences other than those addresses by the teacher, and the teacher's intentions were partially fulfilled. Not only what teacher says, but also how the teacher acts is important to help students understand what to learn from laboratory exercise. The capacity of teachers and schools to advance the learning goals of laboratory experiences is affected by laboratory facilities and supplies and the organization of schools [10]. Direct observation and manipulation of many aspects of the material world require adequate laboratory facilities, including space for teacher demonstrations, student laboratory activities, student discussion, and so on. The importance of chemistry teaching is effective teaching and learning of science involves a perpetual state of show and tell. Good schools combine classroom teaching with laboratory experiment to ensure that their students grasp each and every concept thoroughly [11]. It is also believed that laboratory teaching and experiments that are being conducted there help encourage deep understanding in students. Students are able to retain the knowledge for longer when they see the experiments being performed in front of their eyes. Science chemistry lab equipment allows students to interact directly with the data gathered. They get a first-hand learning experience by performing various experiments on their own. Students are made to use the models and understand different scientific theories and concepts. It is also found that school science lab equipment and supplies make teaching and learning easy both for the teachers, as well as for the students. There are several scientific theories and concepts that are difficult to explain directly from the books, anatomy models, physics science kits, and chemistry science kits for instance make it easy to understand the otherwise complex theories of science. Better facilities will affect the quality of education in schools, but evidence concerning this assumption is often not considered or even known [12]. The advance and well equipped chemistry laboratories are need of students at secondary level, when the laboratories are not properly equipped; the problem arises for practical performance and learning. The laboratories are the bridge for developing the scientific attitude among students. In this regard, the problems

regarding facilities in the chemistry laboratories and to overcome the gap for teaching learning process in schools under this research. The chemistry laboratories are source of teaching, learning for practical understanding. Laboratory work is essential for promoting students learning. The research is based on the facilities provided in the chemistry laboratories of schools for the improvement and for the enhancement of quality of laboratories by using advance equipment by which students perform practical work and develop their scientific attitude. This research study is Limited to comparison between two schools Public school (MUET) and Model school (old campus of Sindh University) at secondary level. Chemistry laboratories are mainly focused throughout the research. The research is limited to the schools running under universities authorities in this study [13]. In profitable organizations, management's primary function is the satisfaction of a range of stakeholders. This typically involves making a profit (for the shareholders), creating valued products at a reasonable cost (for customers), and providing great employment opportunities for employees. In nonprofit management, add the importance of keeping the faith of donors. In most models of management and governance, shareholders vote for the board of directors, and the board then hires senior management. Some organizations have experimented with other methods (such as employee-voting models) of selecting or reviewing managers, but this is rare. Given the scale of most commercial operations and the lack of mechanized record-keeping and recording before the industrial revolution, it made sense for most owners of enterprises in those times to carry out management functions by and for themselves. But with growing size and complexity of organizations, a distinction between owners (individuals, industrial dynasties or groups of shareholders) and day-to-day managers (independent specialists in planning and control) gradually became more common. As the general recognition of managers as a class solidified during the 20th century and gave perceived practitioners of the art/science of management a certain amount of prestige, so the way opened for popularized systems of management ideas to peddle their wares. In this context many management fads may have had more to do with pop psychology than with scientific theories of management.

2. Research Methodology

The significant part of research is methodology, it solves research problems systematically. Research design in this paper is consisted of following points. The tools and methods used for data gathering, Sampling and sampling procedure. The techniques and methods used for data

analysis. These research designs are discussed for achieving the objectives. For research work, there is various methods, however this study is conducted to use quantitative research method, which is commonly used method. The very important Flow chart for research methodology is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Flow chart for research methodology

2.1 *Research approach*

Research approaches are plans and the procedures for research that span the steps from broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection, analysis, and interpretation. This plan involves several decisions, and they need not be taken in the order in which they make sense to me and the order of their presentation here. The overall decision involves which approach should be used to study a topic. Informing this decision should be the philosophical assumptions the researcher brings to the study; procedures of inquiry (called research designs); and specific research methods of data collection, analysis, and interpretation. The selection of a research approach is also based on the nature of the research problem or issue being addressed, the

researchers' personal experiences, and the audiences for the study. Thus, in this book, research approaches, research designs, and research methods are three key terms that represent a perspective about research that presents information in a successive way from broad constructions of research to the narrow procedures of methods.

2.2 Quantitative research method

The quantitative research method is the utilization of testing procedures whose discoveries may be communicated numerically, are interested in scientific control empowering the researcher to measure future occasions or amounts and information gathering. Quantitative method is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into useable statistics. Quantitative data is more framed work as compared to Qualitative method. Quantitative data collection methods include various forms of surveys– questionnaire, face-to-face interviews, telephone interviews, systematically observations (Susan E. Wyse 2011). Objectives which included in this research work can be tested by means of Quantitative method. As the questionnaire is used for collection of data, so careful analysis is needed, which can be done through SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) to analyze the Chemistry laboratories facilities and teaching learning effectiveness in Model school (Elsa Kazi Campus) and Mehran public Schools Hyderabad. As quantitative research is in actual fact about collecting numerical data to clarify an exacting occurrence, particular question seem straight away suitable to being answered using quantitative methods. Point greater than the study examined Quantity is to order highlights, and verified, and the development of realistic models in an attempt to clarify what I saw. The aim of the investigation is to make quantitative and logical use of the models and theories and / or speculation identify phenomena. Estimation method must be quantitative investigation because it gives the basic relationship between the subtle distinctions and associations to investigate the flow quantity. Exchange and interest and social sciences and tin issues, and is used on a large scale quantitative screening as a key aspect of the brain aware of, and useful, and to promote, and the collection of well-being and prosperity of the human race, political science and progress, and less routinely in the humanities and history. To request an exploratory science, for example, physical science is in the same vein "quantitative" by definition, but this use of the term differentiate in contact. In sociology, and decide to reach with test methods, starting position in each of the authentic and philosophical estimates Foundation, which is unique for self-test methodology. Resume frameworks produce information just on

particular cases considered, and any more broad conclusions are just theory. Can be utilized quantitative measures to check any of these hypotheses is valid. Exploration scheme is an effective arrangement for the study of empirical question. Study scheme decide this type of study (enlightening, and semi-testing, experimental, and auditing, beyond the methodological) and this type of subcontractors (for example, Faten case longitudinal), and investigate, and plan an exploratory study, and if, and to create strategies for the accumulation of information and the order of investigation measurable.

Exploration scheme is a system which made access to the responses to the research questions. In the trial plan, a specialist in trying to effectively change the circumstances and conditions, or the experience of the members of the (control), which could lead to changes in behavior or reactionary members in the study. The analysts named it by members of the arbitrary distinctive circumstances, which measures the variables of interest and try to control the bewildering variables. Thus, the investigations regularly changed to a remarkable degree even before they begin to gather information. In a decent trial plans, a few things of incredible having great values in the society. For the first importance, it is important to think about the superior to give the variables that will be measured approach. In this way, you have to look at how they will measure the variable (s), and in addition to the technologies that will be the most suitable to answer the question of exploration. Moreover, you should consider realistic study. Thus, scientists should look at what the wishes of the study and how to achieve this result. After a long wait, the test plan must Scientists think in pragmatic cells including the possibility of access to members and illustrative of how the members of the objective and the masses. It is very important to look at each of these variables before starting the analysis. Moreover, many analysts benefit from the screening test before power steering, so as to make a decision on how large they should be role models for the discovery of the effect of a certain size outline provided with the possibility sought to make the kind of first or second type slipping.

Analysis of evidence case is considered the most difficult and least developed of the research case study section (Yin, 2009). On the other hand, taking into reflection type of data collected, which is quantitative data and ensure ready and equitable evidence case analysis, research a systematic pattern of data analysis through the application of strategy and specific technique for data processing analysis process and to overcome any related difficulties. The research analysis process begins by applying the analysis strategy and therefore suitable for data analysis

technique applied. When information is gathered, the following step is to examine the information, first there is have to arrange methods for breaking down information, preceding behavior examination. Information investigation and understanding is the methodology of allocating intending to the gathered data and deciding the conclusions, hugeness, and ramifications of the findings. Once data is accumulated in test, there is have to be outlined and composed the information and diverse strategies requisitioned abridging and sorting out quantitative and subjective information, after the information has been gathered, the quantitative information, was coded and nourished to SPSS in order to disentangle further undertakings. The information was investigated utilizing straightforward factual apparatuses, for example: tables and rate.

3. Results and Discussion

The analysis and findings achieved from data is included in this section and are discussed in details. This is the method of contracting a great amount of collected data to make it easy; it is an element of research in which the researcher reaches to particular result and interested objectives after analysis and findings with discussions. This is very important and basic chapter of analysis, through which results, conclusion and recommendation can be made by the researcher. In the research work the main focus is that how well the analysis of data takes place. A different form of data and the related approach, techniques and conclusion which has been drawn from the data is needed to be documented properly in this chapter. It is very important for a professional to have data analyzing skill. The data, which is in raw collected state, without any process, have very little value and use. Though this practice of data analyzing, raw data is managed or sequenced in such a way that is useful information is derived from it. Data is analyzed through two angles for this research work; the secondary data analyses and primary data analyses. The secondary data is used to discover the literature for the research work. Secondary data is not highly validated and reliable for conclusion of research work, therefore analyses of primary data takes place. The model & mehran public school labs observation check list is given in the Table 1&2 respectively.

Table 1 Model school labs observation check list

S.no	Equipment and chemicals	Available	Not-available
1.	Barometer; complete with show cases		✓
2.	Beaker	✓	
3.	Test Tube	✓	
4.	Bunsen burners	✓	
5.	Burette	✓	
6.	Burette brushes		✓
7.	Burette clamps	✓	
8.	Burette stand	✓	
9.	Calorimeter		✓
10.	Capillary tubes	✓	
11.	Conical flask	✓	
12.	Crucible		✓
13.	Dishes (China)		✓
14.	Distillation apparatus	✓	
15.	Droppers	✓	
16.	Evaporation dishes		✓
17.	Filter papers	✓	
18.	Filter Pump		✓
19.	Flask-flat Bottom		✓
20.	Flask-round Bottom	✓	
21.	Glass funnel		✓
22.	Glass jars	✓	
23.	Graduated pipette	✓	
24.	Hand gloves		✓
25.	Ignition tubes	✓	
26.	Litmus paper blue pkt	✓	
27.	Litmus paper red pkt	✓	
28.	Stirrer	✓	
29.	Measuring cylinder ; Glass	✓	
30.	Measuring flask	✓	
31.	Melting point apparatus	✓	
32.	Oven		✓
33.	Periodic table (charts)		✓
34.	PH Paper		✓
35.	PH-meters		✓
36.	Physical balance	✓	
37.	Reagent bottle	✓	
38.	Round bottom flask	✓	
39.	Sodium silicate	✓	
40.	Spatulas		✓
41.	Spirit lamp		✓
42.	Stands	✓	

Table 2 Mehran public school labs observation check list

S.no	Equipment and chemicals	Available	Not-available
1.	Barometer; complete with show cases	✓	
2.	Beaker	✓	
3.	Test Tube	✓	
4.	Bunsen burners	✓	
5.	Burette	✓	
6.	Burette brushes	✓	
7.	Burette clamps	✓	
8.	Burette stand	✓	
9.	Calorimeter	✓	
10.	Capillary tubes	✓	
11.	Conical flask	✓	
12.	Crucible	✓	
13.	Dishes (China)	✓	
14.	Distillation apparatus	✓	
15.	Droppers	✓	
16.	Evaporation dishes	✓	
17.	Filter papers	✓	
18.	Filter Pump	✓	
19.	Flask-flat Bottom	✓	
20.	Flask-round Bottom	✓	
21.	Glass funnel	✓	
22.	Glass jars	✓	
23.	Graduated pipette	✓	
24.	Hand gloves	✓	
25.	Ignition tubes	✓	
26.	Litmus paper blue pkt	✓	
27.	Litmus paper red pkt	✓	
28.	Stirrer	✓	
29.	Measuring cylinder ; Glass	✓	
30.	Measuring flask	✓	
31.	Melting point apparatus	✓	
32.	Oven	✓	
33.	Periodic table (charts)	✓	
34.	PH Paper	✓	
35.	PH-meters	✓	
36.	Physical balance	✓	
37.	Reagent bottle	✓	
38.	Round bottom flask	✓	
39.	Sodium silicate	✓	
40.	Spatulas	✓	
41.	Spirit lamp	✓	
42.	Stands	✓	

3.1 Student responses

The comparison is shown in bar chart graph. The respondent says that Mehran public secondary school has equipped with better laboratories facilities. In the Model school main focus is one theoretical work as compared to the practical knowledge. The only text books are given the priorities during the study period. Figure 2&3 shows analysis of the laboratories and responses comparison between Mehran School and model school respectively. The Figure 4 shows the practical performance of the model school which were conducted once in a week.

Figure 2 Laboratories comparison between Mehran School and Model School

Lower managers include supervisors, section leaders, forepersons and team leaders. They focus on controlling and directing regular employees. They are usually responsible for assigning employees' tasks, guiding and supervising employees on day-to-day activities, ensuring the quality and quantity of production and/or service, making recommendations and suggestions to employees on their work, and channeling employee concerns that they cannot resolve to mid-level managers or other administrators. First-level or "front line" managers also act as role models for their employees. In some types of work, front line managers may also do some of the same tasks that employees do, at least some of the time. For example, in some restaurants, the front line managers will also serve customers during a very busy period of the day. Management (or managing) is the administration of an organization, whether it is a business, a not-for-profit organization, or government body. Management includes the activities of setting the strategy of an organization and coordinating the efforts of its employees (or of volunteers) to accomplish its

objectives through the application of available resources, such as financial, natural, technological, and human resources. The term "management" may also refer to those people who manage an organization - individually: managers. Middle managers - examples of these would include branch managers, regional managers, department managers and section managers, who provide direction to front-line managers. Middle managers communicate the strategic goals of senior management to the front-line managers.

Figure 3 Response in Mehran School is high for the availability of equipment than the Model school.

Figure 4 The practical performance in Model school is conducted mostly once a week.

3.2 Teacher's Responses

The graph in the Figure 5 is showing that mostly teachers of Mehran School are satisfied in the labs facilities and for text books use during teaching. There is no any multimedia technology available in both schools.

Figure 5 Laboratories comparison between Mehran School and Model School

Below graphs in Figure 6&7 are the respondents of Mehran school which are showing that first aid box available in the laboratories and proper funds availability and utilization of funds more than Model school.

Figure 6 Response in Mehran School is high for the availability of equipment than the Model school.

Figure 7 The practical performance in Model school is conducted mostly once a week.

Take a look at the box. Here graph shows the no of participants for condition 1 (model) is N 46 and condition 2 (mehran) is 44. The t test is used for comparative analysis; the t test result is showing result of every factor, in a detailed way. The group statistics of the findings in our research are given in the Table 3.

Table 3 Group statistics of the findings

	school	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Do the teachers use text books during teaching in class(chemistry)	model school sindh	46	1.4783	.50505	.07447
	mehran public school	44	1.4318	.50106	.07554
Are the textbooks helpful?	model school sindh	46	1.3696	.48802	.07195
	mehran public school	44	1.4091	.49735	.07498
Are the chemistry laboratories available in the school?	model school sindh	46	1.0870	.28488	.04200
	mehran public school	44	1.1136	.32104	.04840
is multimedia available in chemistry class?	model school sindh	46	1.8913	.31470	.04640
	mehran public school	44	1.2727	.45051	.06792
Are the experiments properly performed in the labs?	model school sindh	46	1.1522	.36316	.05354
	mehran public school	44	1.3864	.49254	.07425
Are the chemicals available in labortory for each experiments?	model school sindh	46	1.3043	.46522	.06859
	mehran public school	44	1.0909	.29080	.04384
Are the equipment available in the labarotry for each experiment?	model school sindh	46	1.5000	.50553	.07454
	mehran public school	44	1.1364	.34714	.05233
Is the first aid box available in the labortory?	model school sindh	46	1.6957	.46522	.06859
	mehran public school	44	1.7500	1.18371	.17845
Do the teachers give you homework?	model school sindh	46	1.6087	.57651	.08500
	mehran public school	44	2.8182	.58161	.08768
how many days in a week you performed practical?	model school sindh	46	1.6087	.49344	.07275
	mehran public school	44	1.0000	.00000	.00000
Are you satisfied with availblity of chemicals and equipment in the chemistry labs?	model school sindh	46	1.7174	.45524	.06712
	mehran public school	44	1.7273	.75832	.11432

This paper includes a set of concluding statements and entitlements based on combinations of the study findings, analysis, and interpretations, it includes summary of findings. In Model School latest equipment are reliable instruments on which teachers do their works. There is lack of health safety instruments too. No proper first aid facility available there. Students are mostly dissatisfied with practical performance. Teachers are also facing problems due to unavailability of chemicals and equipment during performance of practical. No home works on daily basis in the school. There are health safety instruments such as proper first aid facility available. Students are mostly satisfied with practical performance. Teachers are mostly satisfied during performance of practical and homework on daily basis.

Following suggestions/ recommendations needed to be considered for forming in Mehran public school and Model schools. These recommendations are based on findings and literature review: There is need of proper chemistry laboratories facilities at secondary level of schools to develop the basic scientific attitude among the students. The availability of latest equipment must be assured by the school authority. There should be regular check and balance of school laboratories by school administration. The chemicals should be properly labeled in the laboratory. The teacher should be highly qualified and must be trained. The students have lots of awareness about laboratories equipment, that they can give best performance in future in the field of science.

5. Conclusion

It is concluded that the availability of chemistry laboratories are not only the solution, but the properly equipped and well managed chemistry laboratories are the need of schools where the chemicals according to the need of experiments and course content should be available. School laboratory activities have special potential as media for learning that can promote important science learning outcomes for students. Teachers need knowledge, skills, and resources that enable them to teach effectively in practical learning environments. They need to be able to enable students to interact intellectually as well as physically, involving hands-on investigation and minds-on reflection. Students' perceptions and behaviors in the science laboratory are greatly influenced by teachers' expectations and assessment practices and by the orientation of the associated laboratory guide, worksheets, and electronic media. Teachers need ways to find out what their students are thinking and learning in the science laboratory and classroom.

Teachers need to learn new techniques to improve the learning methods and Funds utilization in a proper way is very necessary.

References

1. Azmat, R. (2011)"Manufacturing of High Quality Teachers for Chemistry Education at Higher Secondary Level in Current Era" (PDF). *Pakistan Journal of Chemistry*.
2. Blosser, Patricia E. (2010). A Critical Review of the Role of the Laboratory in Science Teaching. Columbus, OH: ERIC Clearinghouse for Science, Mathematics, and Environmental Education.
3. Boghai, Davar M. (April 2001). A Comparison of the Effects of Laboratory and Discussion Sequences on Learning College Chemistry. *Dissertation Abstracts*, 39(10), 6045A.
4. Bybee, R. (2000). Teaching science as inquiry, In J. Minstrel, & E. H. Van Zee (eds.). *Inquiring into inquiry learning and teaching in science*, pp. 20-46. Wasington DC: American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS).
5. Comber, L. C. & J. P. Keeves. (2000). *Science Education in Nineteen Countries, International Studies in Evaluation I*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
6. Duit, R. (2006). "Bibliography—STCSE (Students' and Teachers' Conceptions and Science Education)". *Kiel:IPN—Leibniz Institute for Science Education*.
7. Duit, R.; Niedderer, H.; Schecker, H. (2007). "Teaching Physics". In *Abell, Sandra K.; Lederman, Norman G. Handbook of Research on Science Education*. Lawrence Erlbaum. p. 599. ISBN 978-0-8058-4713-0.
8. Fay, Paul J. (August 2005). The History of Chemistry Teaching in American High Schools. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 8(8), 1533-1562.
9. Gage, N. L., et al. (2006). *Handbook of Research on Teaching*. Chicago: Rand McNally & Co.
10. Godomsky, Stephen F., Jr. (2011). Programmed Instruction, Computer-Assisted Performance Problems, Open Ended Experiments and Student Attitude and Problem Solving Ability in Physical Chemistry Laboratory. *Dissertation Abstracts*, 31(11), 5873A.
11. Grozier, Joseph E. Jr. (2007). The Role of the Laboratory in Developing Positive Attitudes toward Science in a College General Education Science Course for Nonscientists. *Dissertation Abstracts*, 31(11), 2394A

12. Hofstein, A. & Lunetta, V, N. (2004). The laboratory in science education: Foundation for the 21st century. *Science Education*, 88, 28-54.

13. Hofstein, A., Levi-Nahum, T., & Shore, R. (2001). Assessment of the learning environment of inquiry-type laboratories in high school chemistry. *Learning Environments Research*, 4, 193-207.

Acknowledgments

All praises and thanks are to be the God Almighty.

Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. *TWASP, NY, USA*. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Assets of publishing with NAAR

- Global archiving of articles
- Immediate, free online access for all
- Rigorous peer review process
- Authors retain copyrights
- DOI for all articles

<https://twasp.info/journal/home>

Submit your article : editor@twasp.info